

Overview on Interpersonal Communication and Phenomenological Approaches in Health Care

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Article Info	Abstract
<p>Article History</p> <p>Received: May 21, 2021</p> <p>Accepted: December 23, 2021</p> <hr/> <p>Keywords : Qualitative, Phenomenology, Healthcare, Interpersonal Communication</p> <p>DOI: 10.5281/zenodo.5802558</p>	<p><i>Phenomenology is one of the qualitative research methodology approach. The phenomenological approach is concerned with the subjectivity of the observer, but does not have to be limited to the individual level. Phenomenologist are interested to share a similar understanding of the world and how to build intersubjective spheres. This is an implicit response to what the world looks like and is sometimes referred to as the life world. This article outlines phenomenological approaches related to health research. A phenomenological methodology that describes and directs experiences that apply specifically to a person's illness experience in order to clarify that experience and allow healthcare providers to better understand it. Healthcare interviews and observations allow researchers to identify and understand data from participants' living experiences using a phenomenological approach.</i></p>

Introduction

Qualitative research is an immeasurable knowledge of the human environment. It is a way to give words and meaning to symbolic interactionism. It seeks the perspective of research participants and interprets their understanding of their life experiences and events. There are several qualitative research strategies used in health research. Qualitative methodologies are always more suitable than quantitative methodologies, assuming that the answers found in the study depend on the circumstances in which the individual lives or are expected from some constructed reality. In addition, the methodology used was determined according to the research questions raised (Creswell, 1988, 2007; Smith, Flower & Larkin 2009). This review focuses on qualitative research methods to examine the doctor's experience with patients in order to gain a deeper understanding of certain phenomena and to correlate their experiences. Transforming subjective experience into expressions that allow interpretation and reveal more general insights beyond the phenomena under study. Qualitative research involves an approach to an interpretive and naturalistic world that examines things in the natural environment while trying to interpret phenomena in terms of the meaning they give (Denzin & Lincoln, 2000). Qualitative methods help researchers better understand the rich lives of people and the world they live in through scrutiny. Qualitative research questions often start with how or what, giving researchers a deeper understanding of what is happening in relation to the doctor's interpersonal communication skills (Patton, 2002; Seidman, 1998). Focusing on investigating and understanding how physicians experienced interpersonal communication, understanding the actual experience when examining the subject's involvement in the phenomenon under study, and then on the perspectives they had. Report (Miller, 2005).

Phenomenology Approach

Phenomenology provides a way to acquire empirical knowledge that is descriptive, interpretive, and memory (reflexive) in nature (Morse and Richards, 2002). Bogdan & Biklen (1992) defined phenomenology as an approach to research that seeks to understand the meaning of human interaction events or phenomena and most of them in all situations. Meriam (1998) stated that phenomenology emphasizes the process of extracting meaning from the experiences and interpretations of certain people. In conducting this study, researchers focus on the nature and structure of the experience studied (Creswell, 2013; Dowling, 2005). Phenomenological research focuses on real-life subjects and understands how people view themselves and the world around them in order to discover practical knowledge, possibilities and understandings of phenomena. We always point out the need (Willis, 2007; Polit & Beck, 2008). Phenomenology explains the "what" and "how" of the phenomena an individual experiences and creates an explanation of the essence of the experience, but does not explain or analyze them (Creswell, 2013).

Phenomenology is less interested in analysis and classification than allowing phenomena to exist and develop without interpretation based on previous experience. Phenomenology is a philosophy, and one of the methods in the tradition of qualitative research lies in the interpretation paradigm, developed by positivists or social thinkers who were dissatisfied with the positivist position. The interpretation paradigm takes into account "the subjective importance of individuals involved in social behavior" (Miller, 2005). The phenomenological approach is often referred to as one of the most important traditional approaches of the qualitative paradigm (Creswell, 1998 & 2007). Dowling (2007) pointed out that great phenomenologists developed philosophy in various paradigms. Husserl was originally a positivist, Martin Heidegger (1889-1976) was an interpretist, and Hangeorg Gaddmer (1900-2002) was a constructivist. Nevertheless, general phenomenological studies aim to find a subjective understanding of an individual experience about a term or phenomenon and to find the meaning that emerges from that particular experience in a person's life. Phenomenology reconstructed philosophical questions that arose from everyday life and pervaded various scientific disciplines (Creswell 1998; Miller 2005; Wonjnar & Swanson 2007).

Phenomenology studies the structure of the conscious experience of human experience. Phenomenology is a philosophy closely related to ontology, epistemology, logic, and ethics (Stanford Encyclopedia of Philosophy, 2005). Scientists believe that there are many ways in a researcher's work experience through interaction with other researchers. When the meaning of meaning is formed, a real experience is born (Greene, 1978). There is no doubt that reality was created through human experience (Berger & Luckman, 1967). As suggested by Spiegelberg (1965) & Merriam (1998), there are six phenomenological processes of work that can be performed. i) Researchers need to understand the depth of phenomenological analysis. ii) Study or explore a similar environment as an example of the phenomenon under study to gain complete knowledge of what to study. iii) Look carefully and try to understand the nature of the relationship between ratings. When studying the meaning of a phenomenon, point out not only the problems raised, but how the phenomenon occurs. iv) Explore the importance of the phenomenon by focusing not only on the issues raised, but also on how they occur. v) Try to understand how to study intriguing phenomena. vi) By excluding existing beliefs (enclosed in parentheses), researchers can interpret the meaning of phenomena from the perspective of the research subject, and researchers can interpret data such as origin.

Trust is critical to healthcare because it provides patients with a positive experience in the face of vulnerabilities and uncertainties. One study showed that patient trust assesses the relative importance of interpersonal communication compared to system perception. Scientists understand why this is the case, and despite this advantage of interactivity for trust, there remains a lack of research that utilizes phenomenological theories and methods (Brown, 2009). Year). This helps to understand the essential rationality of general decision making and emphasizes the store manager's active role in building his or her beliefs. Gopnik (2000) investigated the phenomenology she calls the "theory-building system" and developed an analogy to biological systems that seem to embody both drive and clear phenomenology. In discussing this phenomenology, how scientists can combine psychological and philosophical questions to take into account developmental and learning aspects, including consideration of the evolutionary value of explanations, and Explain why it can most often be considered as a similar drive in many respects, a familiar physiological drive in relation to diet, hydration, and gender.

Hermeneutic and Transcendental Phenomenology

Underneath the phenomenological approach that exists, there are several different perspectives. The most orthodox, supported by Husserl's original ideas, is transcendental or descriptive phenomenology as Husserl's philosophy itself has changed (Cohen, 1987). Husserl switched from differentiating the reality of being "there" to phenomenology, which emphasizes both the objective and subjective aspects of experience. Finally, he formulated the phenomenology dominated by subjectivity, making subjectivity the source of objectivity. In short, phenomenology has been convinced as a universal foundation of philosophy and science (Cohen 1987). Husserl pointed out that "intentionality" is the key to what is being investigated, and "consciousness" is the starting point for building knowledge about reality. Researchers need to use the "bracket technique" to make their own judgments or beliefs about the phenomenon and look for the structure of meaning or "essence".

In phenomenology, it is detailed to enrich an individual's experience while at the same time giving the phenomenon of interest to the researcher individuality and uniqueness. The reason for the choice was that, among other things, the phenomenological approach offered the possibility to examine the life experiences of several individuals. Some scholars point out that the hermeneutic phenomenological approach has both descriptive and interpretive elements. Because researchers explain living experiences presented by people and interpreted or understood from the meaning of those experiences (Halkett, Arbon, Scutter & Brog 2007; Van Manen, 1990; Wilkins & Woodgate, 2007). According to van Manen (1990), hermeneutics phenomenology aims to "clarify and explain the structure of the internal semantic structure of living experiences by asking about the nature of a particular experience. The experience presented by must be explained and interpreted in order to fully and better understand the meaning of the experience. It is also very important to understand people's

experiences with your content (Wilkins & Woodgate, 2007). This approach focuses on the idea of the essence (essence) or structure (structure) of a phenomenon. This approach is an area of consciousness of one's own experience in examining structure from the first perspective (Stanford Encyclopedia of Philosophy, 2005).

However, in the tradition of hermeneutics philosophy, hermeneutics phenomenology is rooted in the emphasis on the interpretive element rather than the descriptive element. Ajjawi & Higgs (2007) states that hermeneutics phenomenology can be used by researchers to investigate their participation experiences with further abstraction and interpretation, based on their theoretical and personal knowledge. I did. Researchers provided explanations by answering research questions about the phenomenon in detail. In this context, researchers have investigated the phenomenon to answer research questions through "how" and "why" interview questions. Heidegger was one of Husserl's successors, and his philosophy influenced the development of hermeneutics or hermeneutics phenomenology. Witt and Ploeg (2006) critically reviewed nursing research on the expression of rigor. There is no theoretical literature that gave Heidegger's philosophy as the philosophical foundation of their work. Some have referred to Gadamer, who developed hermeneutics as an approach to understanding social life (Miller, 2005). Others have cited both Heidegger's and Gadamer's philosophies as the philosophical foundations of their work. Hermeneutic philosophy evolved from fields that included the interpretation of the Bible and other sacred texts (Miller, 2005; Witt & Ploeg, 2006). Development of a hermeneutic phenomenological approach that includes elements from Husserl and Heidegger's philosophy.

The basis of the philosophy of hermeneutic phenomenology is that knowledge is realized in the interpretation and understanding of the expression of living experience (Hyde, 2005). Its ontological position is that the experience of being is subjective and human beings are interpretive. Therefore, the subjective nature of a person can only be found by interpretation or understanding (Armor, Rivaux & Bell, 2009). Many philosophical hermeneutic thinkers, including Heidegger and Gadamer, argued that the main meaning often lies in the individual treatment of the situation. This is because situations make up an individual, and individuals make up a situation. Because it is a way that humans do not exist in isolation. As a result of this ontological position, Annells (1996) argued that the epistemological position of the hermeneutic phenomenological approach focuses on the epistemological position. Consistent with these concepts, one cannot separate himself from the context in which he is, and these contexts influence people's choices and give meaning to their lives. This assumption shows that brackets are not possible because researchers are also human beings and humans cannot stand outside of prior understanding and experience. Heidegger argued that prior understanding is a structure for existence in the world, and that what a person encounters in life is an indicator of his or her background (Doyle, 2007; Layverty, 2003). Gadamer also believed that understanding was possible only by certain prejudices (Fleming, Gaidys & Robb, 2003). His philosophical position of "universality" is described as a common consciousness between those who express themselves and those who understand (dabo).

Wojnar and Swanson (2007) summarized the concept of hermeneutic phenomenology. Understanding individuals cannot be done in isolation from the culture, social context, or historical era in which they live. Starting from this standpoint, the purpose of hermeneutic phenomenological research is to identify meaning from the eyes of those who are directly involved in the phenomenon and consciously interpret and understand it. In this case, participants and researchers share an understanding of the process of interaction and interpretation. That is, participants and researchers generate an understanding of phenomena in hermeneutic phenomenological studies (Wojnar & Swanson, 2007), and researchers are completely open or available to the phenomenon of interest and the phenomenon. Expected to be sensitive to. To do this, "researchers need to be disciplined, self-reflexive, obscure the understanding of the phenomenon under study, and reveal prejudices and prejudices that may be revealed" (Amour, 2009).

Methodologically, Laverty (2003) found that the main differences between transcendental phenomenology and hermeneutic phenomenology are related to the researcher's position, the process of data analysis, and the similarities in focus such as data collection and sampling. Instead, it showed that it was a matter of rigor or reliability. Technology and understanding of living experience. The main data is usually collected through detailed interviews with open questions. Interview styles do not apply to either approach, but many studies examining hermeneutic phenomenological approaches use conversational and semi-structured interviews. In addition, even written texts from participants may be used as the primary data collection method for some studies (Ajjawi & Higgs, 2007; Drauker, 1999; Brocki & Wearden, 2006). Compared to transcendental phenomenology, hermeneutics phenomenology is more flexible and allows researchers freedom and creativity (Brocki & Wearden, 2006). However, this can be difficult for researchers using this approach, as the interpretation of the text of the story can depend on the focus of the study and the attitude of the researcher, especially in terms of the reliability of the results. (Lopez & Willis, 2004). Witt and Ploeg (2006) warned that it is important to conduct research among philosophical interest groups in order to fully experience rigor. Lopez and Willis (2004) emphasized the link between the method used and the philosophical foundation. The philosophical foundation needs to be the method and trigger of the research process, and the results need to be expressed in a consistent worldview, even if the researcher using the hermeneutic phenomenological approach must be creative. there is.

Hermeneutic Phenomenology Approach in Healthcare

A qualitative perspective using an interpretive phenomenological approach that seeks to understand the importance of the phenomenon of physicians' interpersonal communication skills to the patients studied (Dyche, 2007). Previous studies have shown previous experience with current healthcare professional communication and interpersonal communication skills. Hermeneutics of phenomenology for explaining living experiences (phenomenology) by explaining phenomena and maintaining a strong reference to the subject. Nevertheless, Canadian educator Max van Manen (1990) developed hermeneutics phenomenology as one of the approaches in qualitative education and research. Van Manen (1990) pointed out three specific attitudes that researchers should pursue, such as accepting the phenomenon under study. The identified research activities are: 1) Take a serious interest in us and look at the phenomena that oblige us to the world. 2) Explore a living experience, not conceptualize it. 3) Look back on the main problems that characterize the phenomenon. 4) Explanation of the phenomenon by the technique of writing and paraphrasing. 5) Maintain a strong and directional pedagogical reference to the phenomenon, and 6) balance in the context of the study by considering the part and the whole. (Van Manen, 1990).

The loose structure of hermeneutics encouraged researchers to take the lead in integrating his / her own research activities. Based on a philosophical foundation, this approach may lead to another way of understanding how healthcare professionals practice interpersonal communication with patients. Hermeneutics phenomenology focused on the subjective experience of a particular group of experts and sought to reveal the world that the subject experienced through the stories of their lifeworld. Hermeneutics phenomenology has proven to be a good methodology for investigating learning to convey clinical reasoning in professional practice. Physicians in this study need to share their career experiences. Through in-depth interviews and observations, the literature focused on the phenomenon of physician experience in dealing with the world of patients and the medical world, their professional world, in interpersonal communication skills (Vimala, 2017). Hermeneutics helps to understand the physician's work experience related to care, healing, and wholeness related to the historical, social, and forming implications of well-being and illness. The hermeneutic phenomenological approach is based on the belief that researchers and doctors come to the quest for understanding through their respective backgrounds and generate an understanding of the phenomenon under study in the process of interaction and explanation. On the other hand, the hermeneutic phenomenological approach requires more initiative and innovation from researchers, as van Manen (1990) stated that "the method of phenomenology is that there is no way". increase. However, Van Manen also found that by investigating traditions, body of knowledge, methodological issues, and methodological characteristics, researchers could select and invent appropriate research methods, methods, and procedures for specific research questions.

Detailed interviews are commonly used in health studies to provide a detailed life experience. In particular, he is a cardiologist who communicates with patients through interpersonal communication skills. In the healthcare field, interviews are a good tool if the study is related to interpersonal care or if the evidence available is limited. Researchers have focused on semi-structured interviews with physicians so that informants can share their life experiences and perspectives on research phenomena. Semi-structured interviews are more often used in health-related qualitative studies. Such interviews are characterized by a flexible topic guide that provides a loose structure of open-form questions for exploring experiences and attitudes. In addition, semi-structured interviews help build relationships with doctors and ask them questions about their own work experience, patient views, and explanations. In contrast to interviews, observations collect naturally occurring data to collect direct information about social processes (Silverman2006). In a sense, observation methods help address the problem that what people say is not necessarily what they are doing (Papst& Mays2006). Participant observation is used to observe research participants in the most natural environment possible. A medical observational study examined how interpersonal communication skills are practiced in everyday work life. Observations in qualitative research generally mean staying in the environment for a longer period of time. During the observation, a field note was created focusing on what was observed. The recording process helps determine what the observed event means and answer the survey questions in subsequent data analysis (Bogdan & Biklen, 2007; Pitney & Parker, 2009).

Conclusion

The commonality of the subjects' living experiences was also important for the clarification of Husserl's phenomenology. Husserl regarded the understanding of inter-subjective experience as central to his phenomenological project. This is because the experienced subject had to be experienced not only by the intentional directness correlation of the subject, but also by other behaviors in favor of the problematic approach. I am very interested in how the world is interpreted. In particular, by focusing on the intentionality of the living body, attention was focused on the precognitive aspects of everyday experience, opening up areas of ambiguous meaning that cannot be reduced to inspirational subjectivity and the natural order of things.

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Author would like to share her research knowledge via publishing article and the cost bared by her own.

Authors' Contributions

Author for this article based from different field of expert. Dr Vimala from Human Communication background. Her field of expertise was on interpersonal communication since her doctoral dissertation focused on Interpersonal Communication skills in doctors and patients' communication.

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